

5. *Human Development Report 2016: Human Development for All, summary / United Nations; comp. S.Jahan. - Moscow: The whole world, 2017. - 40 p.*
6. *Statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Belarus 2016 [Electronic resource]: statistical handbook. - Minsk: National Statistical Committee, 2017. - Access mode: www.belstat.gov.by. - Date of access: 3/12/2017.*
7. *National Statistical Committee of Belarus [Electronic resource] / Access mode: <http://belstat.gov.by>. - Date of access: 11/30/2017.*
8. *Prolevskii OV, Osipov G.V. Belarus and Russia: Social Sphere and Socio-Cultural Dynamics \ - Mn .: IAC. - 2016. S. 188 - 202.*
9. *Economic indicators [Electronic resource] / Access mode: <https://ru.tradingeconomics.com> - Date of access: 24.11.2017.*
10. *Official website of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Republic of Belarus [Electronic resource] .- Access mode: <http://www.mintrud.gov.by/en>. - Date of access: 12/03/17*
11. *Statistical Yearbook of the Republic of Belarus / National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus; Seldom: V.I. Zinovskiy [and others]. - Minsk, 2016. - 715 p.*
12. *Labor and employment in the Republic of Belarus, 2015 (statistical compilation) // National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus (official site) [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: www.belstat.gov.by. - Date of access: 03.12.17.*

ДАНИ ПРО АВТОРА

Базильова Марина Миколаївна, кандидат економічних наук, доцент, доцент кафедри економічної політики Білоруського державного економічного університету;
220037 м.Мінськ, 2-й провулок Багратиона 17-195.
e-mail: basyleva@mail.ru

ДАНИЕ ОБ АВТОРЕ

Базылева Марина Николаевна, кандидат экономических наук, доцент, доцент кафедры экономической политики Белорусского государственного экономического университета;
220037 г. Минск, 2-й переулок Багратиона 17-195.
e-mail: basyleva@mail.ru

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Marina Bazyleva, PhD, associate professor, assistant professor of economic policy of the Belarusian State University of Economics;
220037, Minsk, 2nd lane Bagration 17-195.
e-mail: basyleva@mail.ru

УДК 681.518:911.375–043.86

РОЛЬ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМ В РАЗВИТИИ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ГОРОДА

Дрок П.В.

Ключевые слова: информационные системы, информационно-технологические средства, информационная деятельность, информационные средства.

РОЛЬ ІНФОРМАЦІЙНИХ СИСТЕМ В РОЗВИТКУ СУЧАСНОГО МІСТА

Дрок П.В.

Предметом дослідження є теоретичний аспект інформаційних систем у розвитку міста. Метою дослідження є пошук методів вдосконалення вітчизняних інформаційних засобів у розвитку сучасного міста.

Методи дослідження. У роботі застосовано сукупність наукових методів і підходів, у тому числі системний, структурний, порівняльний, факторний, що дозволило реалізувати концептуальну єдність дослідження.

Результати роботи. Визначено особливості реалізації вітчизняної інформаційної діяльності та методів вдосконалення вітчизняних інформаційних засобів для економічного розвитку країни. Доведено, що для успішного вирішення проблем інформатизації освіти України доцільно комплексно проводити дослідження за вище зазначеними напрямками з широким залученням до

виконання цієї роботи наукових установ України та вищих навчальних закладів. Аналіз напрямків реформування освіти і можливостей застосування інформаційних технологій під час їх здійснення, дає підстави стверджувати, що вирішальним чинником досягнення основних цілей реформування міста є його інформатизація. Ефективні системи інформатизації міста можуть бути створені, якщо вони базуються на дослідженні видів діяльності, що здійснюються в системі міста, і враховують як сучасний стан, так і можливі трансформації у процесі його реформування, сучасний стан і перспективи розвитку галузі інформаційних технологій, останні досягнення педагогіки, психології та інформаційних технологій в цілому.

Галузь застосування результатів роботи. Розвиток міста.

Ключові слова: інформаційні системи, інформаційно-технологічні засоби, інформаційна діяльність, інформаційні засоби.

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN MODERN CITY DEVELOPMENT

Drok P.V.

The subject of research is theoretical aspect of informational systems in city's development.

The goal of research is to find methods of improving of domestic informational means in modern city's development.

Methods of research. In the article was used a number of scientific methods and approaches, including system, structural, comparative, factorial, that helped to actualize conceptual unity of the research.

Results of research. Special aspects of implementation of domestic informational activity and methods of improving of domestic informational means for economic development of the country were defined. It is proved that in order to successfully solve the problems of informatization of education of Ukraine, it is expedient to carry out comprehensive research in the above mentioned directions with wide involvement of scientific institutions of Ukraine and higher educational establishments in this work. The analysis of the directions of educational reform and the possibilities of using information technologies during their implementation, gives grounds to assert that its informatization is the decisive factor in achieving the main goals of the city's reformation. Efficient city information systems can be created if they are based on the study of activities carried out in the city system and take into account both the current state and possible transformations in the process of its reform, the current state and prospects for the development of information technology, the latest achievements in pedagogy, psychology and information technology in general.

The branch of appliance of results. City's development.

Key words: informational systems, informational and technological means, informational activity, informational means.

Informational systems exist till the moment of society's appearance, since on each stage of its development there is a need in management. The mission of informational system is to overwork information, needed for efficient management of all resources of the organization, to create informational and technical environment for managing its activity.

Informational system can exist without using computer equipment – it is a question of economic practicability.

In any informational system of management three types of task are solved:

- tasks of evaluating of the situation (they might be called tasks of pattern identification);
- tasks of transformation of situation description (calculation tasks, modeling problems);
- decision problems (including optimization).

IS – is a complex of information, hardware-in-the-loop and technological means, means of telecommunication, data base, methods of procedures of data handing, staff management, that implement functions of collecting, passing, processing and accumulation of information for preparing and accepting of efficient management solution. The structure for IS is showed on the painting.

The main goal of IS functioning of different objects and levels of national economy of Ukraine is to increase the management quality, to provide specialists (accountants, economists, managers, inspectors) by needed information for officiating their management functions [7].

In IS complete tasks, realization of which on the base of using of modern management methods, appliance of economic-mathematical methods and models, complex of technical means and informational technologies provide the automatization of performance of management functions and procedures (document creation, accounting, planning, analysis, forming, reporting, making decision).

The basis of activity in management of any object is informational systems, that have complicated construction, structure of which depends on the way of activity and size of the organization.

Nowadays corporates need automatized informational system of accounting on the base of modern means of computing technics, that provides:

- full and in-time meeting of informational needs;
- performance of control and auditing tasks, to get the information about defections;
- analysis and predicting of operational and financial activity of the organization;
- receiving on the base of automatization of efficient management decisions.

The management of the economy is based on information and generates new information. The effectiveness of the economy functioning of any object (enterprise, organization) depends largely on the ability of managers of different levels to carefully prepare and substantiate made decisions. The conditions of a market (competitive) economy place serious demands on the quality, timeliness, completeness, reliability of economic information, depth of analysis of economic indicators.

The informational system not only reflects the functioning of the control object, but also affects it through the control bodies. It is a set of informational processes to meet the informational needs of different levels of decision-making, its purpose is to produce information for use (consumption) by administrative staff machinery. Accordingly, it ensures the accumulation, transfer, preservation, processing and aggregation of «bottom-up» information, as well as the specification of «top-down» information.

The purpose of the IS is to describe the economic object, its states, interactions, which are expressed through economic indicators. It is called to timely submit to the management bodies the necessary and sufficient information for making decisions, the quality of which is ensured by highly effective activity of the control object.

For more than 20 years, the program of building an information society is the subject of program development at the international, national and regional levels aimed at the development of science, education, innovation support systems, informational and communication infrastructure, information resource building.

In developed countries, are adopted documents that bring the interim results of the development of the information society and set new goals. The G-8 countries have the most significance meaning for these issues.

In this regard, the Ukrainian cities are also at the center of the ongoing changes. Intensification of global competition and the development of informational and communication technologies lead to serious changes in the economy of cities, which can be marked as deindustrialization. In developed countries there is a faster growth of the information sector of the economy, causing significant changes in the labor market and in the socio-economic dynamics of cities. According to international experts, about 75% of new jobs in developed countries are today related to one or another form of information processing. As a result of these changes, the economic activity associated with the receipt and processing of information plays an important role in the urban economy, allowing them to be described as «informational».

At the state level, according to the state program «Electronic Ukraine» [1], the main target settings of the program are implemented. However, in our opinion, there appeared a need for the formation and development of a concept that reflects new realities and a wider range of issues aimed at informing the city government – the city program «Electronic City» in the system of e-government, which identifies the relevance of this research.

Issues of government and governance are considered by many researchers, including: A. Golobutskyi, G. Golovko, D. Dubov, S. Dubova, S. Zuev, N. Kornilovska, Yu. Mashkarov, D. Melnyk, O. Orlov, V. Steklov, V. Stepanov, V. Tron, O. Shevchuk, S. Malkonri, R. Traummuller, G. Hughes and others. However, we should admit that at present there is no simple single model of e-government. There is only a set of general requirements, the execution of which citizens that receive services, have the right to expect from the government of the informational age. In addition, the practical implementation of e-government technologies meets a number of problems that are usually neglected in advance [7].

The purpose of the work is to consider the purposes and tasks of the concept of the city target program «Electronic city» in the system of electronic governance.

Informational and communication technologies occupy a central place in the renewal and restructuring of key for the city areas: production, transport, trade, public catering, life, as well as education, health care, city management, leisure and entertainment industry, public catering, life and leisure, mass media, social services, urban economy, social and cultural life, etc. In the conditions of increasing significance of the informational function of the state, public administration bodies have to modify their relations with citizens. The development of the informational society pushes the organization's data to the adoption of the concept of «e-government» [2].

In this sense, e-government is the infrastructure that government agencies must create today to change the way they do their job.

Globalization and the development of the informational society are rapidly changing the appearance of the modern world, and although there is no generally accepted definition of the informational society, most experts agree that its essence determines a series of interrelated processes:

- information and knowledge become an important resource and the real driving force of socio-economic development;
- the market of information and knowledge as a factor of production is formed on the level with the markets of natural resources, labor and capital;
- the share of industries that provide the creation, transmission, processing and use of information is growing rapidly;
- the developed informational infrastructure becomes a condition, determined national and regional competitiveness not less than, for example, transport infrastructure;
- the development and active implementation of new information and communication technologies in all spheres of activity significantly changes the models of education, labor, social life and leisure [6].

The implementation of the state program «Electronic Ukraine» identified several problems:

1. Large work on informatization, conducted in the last decade in cities, is not sufficiently coordinated. In addition to the annual urban information plans, territorial entities have their own programs, plans and projects of informatization, but they have sections related to informatization in various city target programs. The inconsistency and weak coordination of these works lead to the low level of integration of existing systems of city administration and local self-government. There is unjustified duplication of functions in different systems, there is no metropolitan complex of standards, classifiers, metadata sets, etc., which prevents unifying of data representation and ensures the coordinated functioning of these systems. The regions need to develop a unified strategy of informatization of the city, in new effective mechanisms for coordinating this activity, in implementing measures for common system provision of the city's informational and communication infrastructure.

2. Informational and communication technologies are a powerful tool for updating and improving the efficiency of all areas of activity. However, the level of informatization of schools, museums, libraries and other institutions of culture, education and science, which is in charge of the city, remains low. One of the strategic tasks of the movement towards the informational society should be the development and implementation of a set of measures to informatization of the relevant spheres of urban life.

3. Over the last decade, economic growth and job creation in economically developed countries are increasingly dependent on innovation, which implies the successful commercialization of research and development. Moreover, the enterprises of information and communication technologies of the sector, in which the development and commercialization of new technologies is the most important condition of competitiveness, is the most innovative activity. In times of the USSR, Ukraine was the center of the national innovation system, which was formed in conditions of total state ownership and centralized management of the economy. Elimination of Union sectoral ministries, privatization and a severe economic crisis have destroyed this system. The innovative process, established within the framework of the departmental system, was broken, – the organizational structure, which administratively connects production and science and ensures the implementation of developments, disappeared, the market innovations were not fully operative. The overall innovative productivity of cities has also sharply decreased. For a modern city in Ukraine is important not only to maintain its innovative potential but also to form a fully operational and efficiently functioning innovation infrastructure in the city, first of all, in the informational and communication sector itself and through the introduction of informational and communication technologies in other areas.

4. Intensive development of informational and communication technologies, their implementation in all spheres of life of the city and citizens have created new problems – providing information security of the city. Cyberterrorism and cybercrime are new phenomena that require the coordination and unification of the efforts of all those who are interested in counteracting them. In this situation, the development of a modern, world-wide experience, system of information security of the city and a complex of technical and organizational-administrative measures becomes extremely topical.

5. Social differentiation in access to information and communication technology capabilities is a common problem for all cities and countries that have embarked on the road to the information society. This problem has been called the problem of information inequality. Its importance is recognized by all states and international organizations. Access to basic informational and communication services and socially important information should be provided to all citizens, regardless of their place of residence and socio-economic status. Without solving this complicated problem related to technical, economic, cultural

and socio-psychological barriers to the massive use of informational and communication technologies, a successful advance to the information society is impossible.

6. In the conditions of development of the global informational society and orientation of Ukraine to the openness of the economy and full integration into the world economic system, the development of economic and industrial policy of the city that meets new conditions is a topical issue. Important directions of this policy should be the stimulation of the information industry of the city as the most profitable and fast-growing branch of the economy, which creates the preconditions for increasing of competitiveness in all other industries, as well as stimulating the use of informational and communication technologies in the economy, in particular the development of various forms of electronic commerce. Recent years have been characterized by the increased attention given by governments of different countries and regions to more efficient and effective interaction with citizens and organizations on the basis of widespread use of informational and communication technologies, the process of creating so-called electronic governments for the purpose of e-governance in society is held.

The conducted work in Ukraine on informatization was mainly focused on the informational provision of managerial tasks and case management. The interaction of authorities with citizens and business entities on the basis of new informational and communication technologies (ICTs) was not given due attention [5]. The program of informatization of the city administration should be based on the general concept of «e-government», contain a system of organizational, normative-methodical and technical measures that ensure the transition to the electronic form of interaction between the authorities and the population and organizations.

Conclusions. Innovation in the development of informational systems is a constant novelties in the activity of all branches of industry, in the life process – it is the urgent need, without which it will lose its connection with life, lose its creative potential, turn into a routine business, neither need society nor personality Life requires the intensification of search, experimentation, introduction of the latest technologies, the application of new means of development of the city and the country as a whole. However, the implementation of these requirements can not be chaotic, unsystematic, ill-thought and without taking into consideration the experience that in the past led to known, and in many cases, outstanding achievements. In a number of approaches, this experience has not lost its significance even today. It is clear that innovation should be deployed in the light of past experience, and not ignore it. At the core of innovative development must be all the sciences (economics, philosophy, political science, sociology, etc.), which, as well as in other branches of social production, pave the way for practice. According to this we have chosen the problem of informational systems in the elaboration and development of the e-city program as an object of independent theoretical analysis. To successfully solve the problems of informatization of education in Ukraine it is expedient to carry out comprehensive research on the above-mentioned directions with wide involvement of Ukrainian academic institutions and higher educational institutions in carrying out this work. The analysis of the directions of educational reform and the possibilities of using information technologies during their implementation, gives grounds to assert that its informatization is the decisive factor in achieving the main goals of the city's reformation. Efficient city information systems can be created if they are based on the study of activities carried out in the city system and take into account both the current state and possible transformations in the process of its reform, the current state and prospects for the development of information technology, the latest achievements in pedagogy, psychology and information technology in general.

References

1. Kravchenko S. A. *The modern informational technologies - [Electronic resource] - Access mode: <https://forum.pravda.com.ua/index.php? Topic = 864117.0>*.
2. Sergienko A. P. *Informational and communication management in a global society: psychology, technology, and PR-technik - [Electronic resource] - Access mode: <http://mmlib.net/knigi/marketing/kniga-29/>*.
3. Gritsenko G. P. «Information resources» / G.P. Gritsenko // *Textbook. Ed. Gritsenko G.P., 2008. - 401 p. - Bibliogr.: P. 400.*
4. Kholmogorov V. S. *Modern E-city - [Electronic resource] - Access mode: <http://mmlib.net/knigi/marketing/kniga-29/>*.
5. Bilyavtsev M. I., Vorobiov V. N. *Information management / M. I. Bilyavtsev, V. M. Vorobyov // Textbook. Ed. M. I. Bilyavtsev, V. N. Vorobiov. - Kyiv: Center for Educational Literature, 2006. - 407 pp. - Bibliogr.: P. 406.*

6. Pavlenko P. B. *Electronic City* - [Electronic resource] - Access mode: <https://ukurier.gov.ua/en/articles/elektronne-misto-zमितnit-mislennya/>.
7. Tsygankova T.M *Modern models and trends of city development* / T. N. Tsygankova // *Informational systems*, 2004. - №2. - P. 31-36. - Bibliogr.: P. 36
8. Kotler F., Wong V., Sonders J., Armstrong G. *Fundamentals of Informational Systems* / F. Kotler, Veronica Wong, John Sonders, Gary Armstrong // *4th European Edition, Principles of Marketing: European Edition 4th.* - M.: Williams, 2007 - 1200 p. - Bibliogr.: P. 1199
9. Kravtsov A. O. *Electronic city* - [Electronic resource] - Mode of access: <http://gris.com.ua/our-projects/elektronne-misto-2/>.
10. Nikolaiev P. A. *Modern city* - [Electronic resource] - Access mode: <https://www.slideshare.net/mrbrut/ss-62353637>.

ДАНИ ПРО АВТОРА

Дрок Павло Валерійович, кандидат історичних наук, старший викладач кафедри документознавства
ДВНЗ «Переяслав-Хмельницький ДПУ імені Григорія Сковороди»
08401, м. Переяслав-Хмельницький, Вул. Сухомлинського 30
e-mail: drok_pavlo@ukr.net

ДАНИЕ ОБ АВТОРЕ

Дрок Павел Валерьевич, кандидат исторических наук, старший преподаватель кафедры документоведения
ГВУЗ «Переяслав-Хмельницкий ГПУ имени Григория Сковороды»
08401, г. Переяслав-Хмельницкий, ул. Сухомлинского 30
e-mail: drok_pavlo@ukr.net

DATA ON AUTHOR

Pavlo Drok, candidate of Historical Sciences, Senior Lecturer of Document Science Department SHEI «Pereiaslav-Khmelnytskyi Hryhoriy Skovoroda State Pedagogical University»
08401, Pereiaslav-Khmelnytskyi, Sukhomlynskyi str., 30
e-mail: drok_pavlo@ukr.net

УДК 371.2(477)

СУЧАСНИЙ СТАН, ТЕНДЕНЦІЇ ТА ПРОБЛЕМИ РОЗВИТКУ ОСВІТИ В УКРАЇНІ

Кучеренко С.Ю.

В статті проаналізовані сучасний стан, тенденції та проблеми розвитку освіти в Україні. Предметом дослідження є система освіти України.

Метою дослідження є аналіз сучасного стану освіти України, визначення проблем та тенденцій його розвитку на сучасному етапі.

У дослідженні використовувались загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи: аналізу та синтезу, аналогії та порівняння, статистичні, експертних оцінок тощо.

Результати роботи. Обґрунтовано сучасний стан освіти України. Проаналізовано основні показники рівня фінансування освіти в Україні. Визначено, що причинами, які негативно впливають на розвиток системи освіти в Україні є: політична нестабільність в державі, скорочення ВВП та ВНП, недостатній рівень фінансування освітньої галузі (фінансування в основному лише захищених статей), неефективне використання наявних ресурсів та важелів впливу, недосконала правова база, застаріла матеріально-технічна база, несприятливий інвестиційний клімат, неефективне функціонування суспільно-правових інститутів, «відтік мізків за кордон» та інші фактори.

Висновки. Порівнюючи освіту України у перші роки незалежності та сьогодні, можна сказати, що вона зазнала суттєвих змін, а саме в якості освіти, способах викладання та ін.

У світі сьогодні існує багато проблем, але треба починати їх вирішувати саме з освіти, хоча мало хто цілкоміто знає основні проблеми сучасної освіти та напрями їх вирішення. Якщо не вирішити проблеми освіти, то немає резону починати вирішувати інші проблеми, тому що